

Molybdenum. Part III : Thermal Decomposition Studies on Oxo-Molybdenum(V) Complexes

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Several oxo-molybdenum(V) complexes of pyridine carboxylic acids and mixed chelates of pyridine (or derivatives of pyridine) and quinaldinic acid or quinaldinic acid and 1, 10-phenanthroline have been studied thermogravimetrically. The temperature zones have been recorded and several unstable intermediates have also been characterised.

DURING recent years there has been an increased interest in studying the coordination complexes by thermogravimetric technique. This and many other techniques such as differential thermal analysis (DTA), differential thermogravimetry (DTG), thermomagnetic study etc. have been described in the literature for the complexes of Co(II), Co(III), Mn(III), Cr(III), Cu(II), Ni(II), oxo-vanadium(IV) etc. but there is very few report of thermogravimetric analysis on oxo-molybdenum(V) complexes^{1,2}. This paper deals with the thermal decomposition of some of the oxo-molybdenum(V) complexes. The complexes chosen for this purpose are the oxo-molybdenum(V) complexes of pyridine carboxylic acids and mixed ligand complexes of pyridine (or derivatives of pyridine) and quinaldinic acid or quinaldinic acid and 1,10-phenanthroline.

Experimental

The syntheses, characterisation, spectral data, i. r. and magnetic properties have been described earlier^{3,4}. The thermal decomposition for the complexes depicted in fig. 1 was studied in air on a Stanton thermobalance (high temperature model, 1mg. sensitivity) from 0° to 1000° and a scale of 10 percent wt. loss is provided in the figure. The complexes, MoO₂Nic.2H₂O and MoO₂Q.py were studied on the same balance from 0° to 800° and depicted in Fig. 2 on the scale of 5 percent wt. loss basis.

Results and Discussion

The complex, MoO₂ pic. H₂O starts to lose wt. (i.e. water) at around 80° and completed within the range 165°-170° (Calc. 6.7 percent ; Found 6.5 percent). The species, [MoO₂pic] thereafter, shows a stable region upto 225° and then gives a sharp big fall upto 420° in in the TGA curve (Calc. 48.8 percent ; Found 49 percent). The loss at this stage corresponds to a complete removal of picolinic acid. The final product is practically reduced to molybdic acid which is stable upto 800° and then sublimes (Fig. 1. Curve 2). Thus

the dissociation sequence appears to be :

Fig. 1.

1. Dioxo-picolinate molybdenum (V), monohydrate
2. β -Picoline-dioxo-monoquinaldinate-molybdenum (V)
3. μ -Phenanthroline-dioxo-dichloro-diquinaldinate-dimolybdenum(V).

The complex, [MoO₂Q (β -pic)] shows no loss upto 60° and then a very small fall in the curve which is completed at 90°. This corresponds to moisture desorption (Calc. 4.38 per cent ; Found 3 per cent). The anhydrous complex, [MoO₂Q(β -pic)] thereafter, shows a stable region upto 180° and then gives a sharp fall upto 225° where the organic base, β -picoline, is completely lost (Calc. 23.7 per cent ; Found 24 per cent). The decomposition of the latter residue,

[MoO₃Q] began after 225° which is indicated by sharp big fall in the TGA curve and the loss of quinaldinic acid is completed at 420°. (Calc. 57.3 per cent; Found 61.5 per cent) (Fig. 1, Curve 1).

The thermal decomposition curve of [Mo₂O₂Cl₂Q₂(phen)] indicates that the complex suffers no appreciable decomposition upto 200° and chlorine is completely lost at 220° (Calc. 15.95 per cent; Found 16.5 per cent). The evolution of phenanthroline begins after 220° and completes at 315° (Calc. 24 per cent; Found 26 per cent). Total decomposition of the latter, [MoO₂Q] began after 315° and lost all the quinaldinic acid at 545° giving a residue of MoO₃ (Calc. 60.5 per cent; Found, 58 per cent). The MoO₃ is stable upto 800° and then sublimates (Fig. 1, Curve 3).

Fig. 2.

1. Dioxo-nicotinate-molybdenum (V), dihydrate.
2. Pyridine-dioxo-monoquinaldinate-molybdenum(V).

The TGA curve of dioxo-nicotinate-molybdenum(V), dihydrate, [MoO₂Nic.2H₂O] indicates that deaquation is completed at 240° (Calc. 12.59 per cent; Found 13 per cent). The anhydrous complex, [MoO₂Nic] does not lose the entire nicotinic acid at 380°, retains one-third (Calc. 32.8 per cent; Found 32 per cent) which is completely lost at the next stage of decomposition at 620°-630° and goes over to MoO₃ (Fig. 2, Curve 1).

The complex, [MoO₂Q.py] shows no change in the TGA curve upto 50° and thereafter, shows a slow but continuous loss in wt. upto 270°. The loss at this stage corresponds to a complete removal of pyridine forming [MoO₂Q] (Calc. 20.84 per cent; Found, 20 per cent). The species, [MoO₂Q] is stable upto 300° whereafter it suffers decomposition and loses all quinaldinic acid at 350° (Calc. 57.3 per cent; Found, 55 per cent) (Fig. 2, Curve 2).

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